

ABOUT THE MEDICINAL LEAFY SARSABIL PLANT *ASPARAGUS BRACHYPHYLLUS TURCZ*

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Abstract. *The medicinal plant naturally distributed in our republic - Asparagus brachyphyllus Turcz - belongs to the family of Asparagaceae. Information and conclusions about the first-time planting of a perennial plant, its naming, description, and obtained results are given.*

Keywords: *sarsabil, asparagus, cladodia, introduction, cultivation, Asparagus brachyphyllus Turcz.*

Introduction. In recent years, great attention has been paid in our republic to the cultivation of medicinal plants, identifying species at risk of extinction, and implementing measures for their restoration, as well as establishing and expanding plantations.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-4670 dated April 10, 2020, the report says "750 species out of more than 4.3 thousand plants of the local flora are considered medicinal, of which 112 are registered for use in scientific medicine, of which 70 species are actively used in the pharmaceutical industry". This means that it is necessary to conduct a lot of research on local cultivation, procurement and production of medicinal plant products that are in great demand and need, and to do a lot of work in medicine in general, including the cultivation of wild medicinal plants, introduction to technologically suitable areas. Given this, it will be necessary to create new plantations of medicinal plants in ecologically clean areas, taking into account soil and climatic conditions. This will reduce the use of wild plants, and it will be advisable to create plantations in different regions of the republic. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-4901 dated November 26, 2020 also provides for the creation of cultivated plantations of medicinal plants, taking into account specific soil and climatic conditions [11].

The territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is rich in flora, including medicinal plants. According to the World Health Organization, 60% of the available medicines are drugs obtained from raw materials of medicinal plants [10].

The population's need for medicinal plants is increasing every year. Natural areas of medicinal plants are decreasing due to the limited raw material reserves of naturally growing medicinal plants. For this reason, the protection of medicinal plants, the study of their bioecological properties, the correct and rational use of raw materials, the development of scientifically based cultivation technologies are relevant and important. In this direction, with the effective use of the opportunities available in the republic, specific measures are taken to identify mother plants of medicinal and spicy plants, their preservation and use, increase the volume of cultivation, processing, production and export. Therefore, in order to provide the pharmaceutical industry of Uzbekistan with raw materials of local medicinal plants, it will be necessary to develop technologies for growing species of medicinal plants belonging to the local and foreign flora. This will also reduce the import of medicinal plant raw materials.

It is known that the medicinal properties of medicinal plants are not the same everywhere. Preservation or change in the medicinal properties of plants is directly related to the composition of the terrain and natural and climatic conditions. One of the useful properties obtained from the creation of new plantations of unique medicinal plants that are part of the flora of our country (when plants are brought from one place to another (different soil and climate) place, the previous properties of the plants change) is noticed. As already mentioned above, one of the useful, rare and endangered plants is medicinal asparagus (*Asparagus brachyphyllus* Turcz.), growing in our country.

In order to create the possibility of preparing various ancient, rare and forgotten natural medicines, it is necessary to clarify the names and types of recommended medicinal plants. Thus, in some sources, for example, in the book by K. T. Berdiev, M. H. Khakimova, G. B. Makhmudova "Forest Medicinal Plants" it is said: "Asparagus is a perennial plant belonging to the Asparagus family. There are about 200 different types of asparagus. Some of them are herbs, some are small shrubs". These words repeated by M. D. Khamdamova also described "Asparagus as a perennial plant belonging to the Asparagus family" in the article "The chemical composition of the asparagus plant, its importance in folk medicine, the beneficial properties of folic acid", published in the 4th issue of the journal "Economy and Society" for 2021 [1, 7].

Asparagus is a completely different plant, if you refer to the sources on this matter, according to "Dictionary of Russian-Latin-Uzbek medicinal plants" by Kholmatov G.Kh., Kasimov A.Ya. "Curly thistle (blessed) - *Cnicus benedictus* L. - thistle (sariggul). Asteraceae (compound flowers) belong to the Asteraceae (Somrositae) family. This is an annual herbaceous plant growing up to 15-30 cm in height" [9].

Asparagus brachyphyllus Turcz. - sarsabil - belongs to the Asparagus family, Sarsabil is a perennial creeping plant belonging to the Asparagus family L. [8].

There are about three hundred species of *Asparagus* L., all of which differ from each other in appearance. About 10 species of sarsabil are known in Uzbekistan. One of them is the medicinal plant *Asparagus brachyphyllus* Turcz., so named because its leaves are shorter than those of other species. The stem of this plant is often creeping, its length reaches 1-1.5 m. The leaves are small, lanceolate, from the axils of the leaves 2 or 3 more lanceolate leaves and 1 lateral branch (modified branches - cladodes) are formed. The fruit is a round red berry up to 5 mm in diameter. The seeds are compressed on both sides, rounded, with two or more lobes. Pollen flowers are larger than seed flowers, bell-shaped. It blooms in May-July, the fruits ripen in late June-July and fully ripen in August-October. In the wild, it is widespread in our republic in Tashkent, Fergana, Andijan, Samarkand, Navoi, Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Jizzakh regions, and grows in gardens [2, 3, 5, 8, 12, 14].

Asparagus brachyphyllus Turcz. is listed in the Red Book of the Russian Federation and the Transbaikal Territory. [4].

In folk medicine, the rhizome, roots, and young branches of Sarsabil are used. They contain many useful biologically active compounds, vitamins, and microelements. The roots of the plant also contain vitamin C, saponins, the amino acid asparagine, etc. Ripe fruits contain up to 36% sugars, causanthin and physamine, while the seeds contain up to 16% fatty oil [7, 13].

Sarsabil - extracts made from asparagus raw materials are used in folk medicine to treat bladder inflammation, urinary retention, diabetes, infertility, rheumatism, urolithiasis, and heart

rhythm disturbances (arrhythmia). A tincture made from its fruits is prescribed for lethargy in patients. The rhizome, roots and stems are also used for urolithiasis and heart defects [7, 13].

In Chinese folk medicine, sarsabil is recommended for diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, liver, lungs, diabetes, gout, rheumatism and tuberculosis, as an appetite suppressant and digestive agent [7].

In modern medicine, it has been established that sarsabil preparations have a predominantly diuretic effect. In addition, experiments have shown that asparagine and sarsabil extracts reduce blood pressure, support heart function, dilate peripheral vessels, and improve liver function. Sarsabil galenic preparations also have a sedative and expectorant effect. Therefore, these herbal preparations are also prescribed for neuroses, hysteria, tachycardia, atherosclerosis, dysmenorrhea and other conditions [7].

Research methods. In 2024, based on our experience, we implemented the tasks set in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PR-4901 dated November 26, 2020 "On measures to expand the scope of scientific research on the cultivation and processing of medicinal plants, the development of its seed production". *Asparagus brachyphyllus* Turcz was collected in Karakol district of Bukhara region at the end of August 2023. We set ourselves the task of studying the growth and development of medicinal plants by sowing their seeds.

According to the source, the plant *Asparagus brachyphyllus* Turcz was taken for the experiment. As a result of studying scientific and literary sources, it is known that it is necessary to make a number of clarifications regarding the name and description of this species.

In the spring of 2024, the seeds of the plants used in our research were planted in fields of three different conditions for the purpose of comparative study. These are:

- first - the soil in a small experimental area of the Center for Growing and Processing Medicinal Plants (hereinafter referred to as the Center) was shifted to form a steep slope, and over the course of several years, the fertile part of the soil was washed away by rain and snow, 2024.04.04. is the day of sowing numbered seeds;

- the second - on 19.04.2024 the seeds were sown in a small experimental plot of the Center, where the soil is relatively fertile, but rocky, where the shadow of the wall falls from eleven to eleven thirty in the summer, and where the shadow of the tree falls after half past ten;

- the third - 04/17/2024. The numbered seeds were sown on Piskent experimental plot of the Center, where sunlight reaches throughout the day. The soil of this place is considered fertile, but sloping.

The plants planted in the first and second fields were processed and watered in the same way.

Research results. Before planting, the seeds were cleaned, sorted, counted and weighed 1000 seeds. It was found that the mass of 1000 seeds was 18.7 grams.

The small experimental site of the center was on 04/2024/04, germination of seeds of medicinal plants *Asparagus brachyphyllus* Turcz began on the 21st day. During the follow-up observation on April 30, the germination of the sown seeds reached 38%, the height of the seedling was 6 cm, 10 leaves were formed. During the observation on May 31, the germination of the sown seeds reached 96.6%, the height of the sprout was 12 cm, 30 leaves were formed.

During the observation on June 25, the survival rate of the germinated seedlings from the sown seeds averaged 90.6%, the height reached an average of 17.7 cm, an average of 33.3 leaves

were formed, of which the leaves in 7 joints fell off, the number of lateral shoots with the length of 2.7 cm was 3 pcs., the number of leaves 11.

The germination of seeds of experimental plants, which were sown on April 19, 2024 in second place in the small experimental field of the Center, began on the 24th day. During the observation on May 31, the germination of the sown seeds averaged 91.4%, the height of the seedlings reached 7.0 cm, 26 leaves were formed. During the observation period on June 25, the germination rate of planted seeds and survival of sprouts averaged 91.4%, i.e. the seedlings that sprouted from seeds survived completely. The seedling height averaged 16.3 cm and produced 38.7 leaves. It was found that the leaves in 6 segments fell off, the number of cladodes was 7.7, the length was 5.2 cm, and the number of leaves was 14.3.

If we compare the survival rate and development of seedlings that sprouted from seeds planted in two different conditions in close proximity to each other, the table 1 shows that the survival rate of seedlings in the first planting site, where the sunlight is steep and falls for a long time, is relatively low, i.e. 6% of the sprouted seedlings died. This may be due to the scorching heat of the morning sun. The sprouts in the second planting site, which was shaded for most of the day, survived completely. In this case, firstly, seed germination began quickly, and secondly, seed germination began late, and seedling development accelerated in the summer, but the difference between them is relatively small. Based on these results, we can say that the plant is not very selective to the soil (to fully follow this conclusion, it is necessary to study these experiments more carefully, since this plant has not been cultivated at all until now). However, it is known that the plant develops well in fertile soil.

Table 1

Comparative table of survival and development of seedlings germinated from seeds sown in close proximity to each other under two different conditions.

T/r	Time to sow the seed	Bruising (%)	Single stems				Side of branches		
			Quantity (pcs)	Height (cm)	Number of leaves (pcs)		Quantity (pcs)	Length (cm)	Number of leaves (pcs)
					available	The number of joints in which the leaves are shed			
The observation period is May 31, 2024									
1.	2024.04.04	96,6	2,3	10,7	26,3		4,3	2,7	5,0
2.	2024.19.04	91,4	1,3	7,0	25,0		3,3	1,5	3,7
	The difference	-5,2	-1,0	-3,7	-1,3		-1,0	-1,2	-1,3
The period of observation is June 25, 2024									
1.	2024.04.04	90,6	2,7	17,7	33,3	7,0	3,0	2,7	11,0
2.	2024.19.04	91,4	1,7	16,3	32,7	6,0	7,7	5,2	14,3

	The difference	+0,8	-1,0	-1,4	-0,6	-1,0	+4,7	+2,5	+3,3
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The number of joints where the leaves are shed

Asparagus brachyphyllus Turcz was planted on Piskent experimental plot. The germination rate of the medicinal plant was 82 percent. Of these, 41.5% survived until July 2. The average stem height is 3.2 cm, the number of leaves is 5.2 pcs., lateral branches of the first order are 3.4, the length is 1.5 cm, 2. 2.1 lateral branches of the second order with a length of 0.7 cm, 1.2 leaves survived.

The reason for the lack of germination and survival of sprouted seedlings, as well as the slow growth of seeds planted on Piskent experimental plot, was the lack of timely watering in this place. Among the eight species planted here at the same time, the seeds of three plant species germinated and survived. The seeds of one plant species germinated, but did not survive. Four plant seeds did not germinate at all. From this situation it can also be said that sardine is resistant to dehydration.

Summary. Experiments on growing medicinal plants *Asparagus brachyphyllus* Turcz. are being conducted for the first time. The germination of seeds of this plant is good. Based on the above information it can be said that the sarsabil plant is resistant to dehydration and is not very picky.

A thorough study of this plant is required. This is a little-studied medicinal plant, but a unique and very useful medicinal plant that can become the subject of research with great scientific potential. It is necessary to determine its biologically active components. As a result of continuing these studies, excellent soil has been created for obtaining highly effective phytopreparations based on this plant in the future.

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